

The ESA-DLR LUNA Analogue Facility – The Moon on Earth: Status and Future Developments A. Cowley¹, A.E.M.C Casini², J. Schlutz¹, P. Mittler², M. Maurer¹, B. Knappmyer-Endrun², M. Maibaum², C. Fanti-nati² ¹European Space Agency, ²German Aerospace Centre (DLR)

Introduction: In September 2024, the ESA-DLR LUNA facility was officially inaugurated and made available for initial operations. This facility represents a unique European asset for lunar exploration research, providing an advanced platform for simulating lunar surface conditions and testing scientific instruments, rovers, and exploration technologies with a strong emphasis on operations and integrated scenario simulation capability. Situated at the European Astronaut Centre (EAC) in Cologne, Germany, LUNA is a collaborative initiative between the European Space Agency (ESA) and the German Aerospace Center (DLR), directly supporting Europe's exploration ambitions from Low Earth Orbit (LEO) human spaceflight towards planetary exploration, coherent with the ESA Terrae Novae strategy [1].

LUNA complements existing EAC and DLR analogue facilities at the Cologne campus, such as :envihab and the Neutral Buoyancy Facility (NBF). It features a large-scale artificial lunar analogue environment housed within a dedicated hall structure and comprehensive ground segment integration. The key element is a substantial regolith simulat testbed (EAC-1a material), accurately replicating a number of specific lunar soil characteristics [2]. Adjacent environmentally controlled areas also host smaller simulat caches, notably 20t of anorthostic simulat material to compliment the main hall material.

Adjacent to the analogue hall is the Future Lunar EXploration Habitat (FLEXHab)[3], capable of supporting up to four crewmembers for 1-day missions and equipped with direct access to the main regolith testbed.

LUNA enables a range of mission scenario simulations for astronaut training and technological validation and TRL raising, including geological and seismic regolith characterization, In Situ Resource Utilization (ISRU), telerobotics, and preparation for Extravehicular Activities (EVAs). Recent facility expansions emphasize enhanced dust mitigation testing, upgraded telecommunications for remote and autonomous operations, and operational habitat analogues.

Future developments include a dedicated sun simulation capability as well as bespoke gravity of-flooding system. LUNA welcomes collaboration with external research institutes, universities, and industry partners in a collaborative framework, providing low-barrier entry for scientific experiments and technological demonstrations and catalysing exploration preparation activities.

This presentation outlines LUNA's current capabilities, recent open utilisation campaigns, and the future development roadmap.

Fig.1 – Installation of an radio-isotope thermoelectric generator during a surface EVA simulation within LUNA.

Fig. 2 – Testing of geophone system and production of seismic measurements within LUNA testbed.

References:

[1] ESA's Terrae Novae Strategy – https://www.esa.int/Science_Exploration/Human_and_Robotic_Exploration/Exploration/Terrae_Novae_Europe_s_exploration_vision

[2] Zemeny A, Sardisco L, Quinteros S, Mikesell TD, Pirrie D, Rose L, Cowley A and Manick K (2024) The Luna Analog Facility testbeds (ESA, EAC): contemporary characterization work of highland (lunar) and mare (EAC-1) lunar regolith simulants. *Front. Space Technol.* 5:1510635.

[3] FLEXHab, under development by SAGA: <https://www.saga.dk/projects/flexhab>